

A Review Paper on Kawathekar Supermarket Android Application Best Quality Best Price

Vidya B. Maskar
Computer Engineering
SVERI's College of Engineering (Poly),
Pandharpur, India

Pratiksha Shivaji Pawar
Computer Engineering
SVERI's College of Engineering (Poly),
Pandharpur, India

Srushti Sudhir Narayan
Computer Engineering
SVERI's College of Engineering (Poly),
Pandharpur, India

Diksha Dhananjay Tapkire
Computer Engineering
SVERI's College of Engineering (Poly),
Pandharpur, India

Shruti Tukaram Raut
Computer Engineering
SVERI's College of Engineering (Poly),
Pandharpur, India

Abstract:- The Kawathekar Supermarket project deals with robotization of supermarkets. This includes both offer and purchase details. This design was developed with the idea of making the system more reliable, simpler, faster, and more educational. There are many inefficiencies faced by sellers in homegrown systems. Storing accurate and inaccurate information requires maintaining large registers, which can be a messy and tedious process. However, our system reduces paper workshops. On the other hand, homebrew systems have many serious problems. Loss of efficiency has a huge impact on the productivity of everyone who keeps data up to date.

Keywords:- E-Commerce, Shopping Cart, Product, Online Shopping.

I. INTRODUCTION

India has seen an increase in the adoption of online grocery platforms in recent times due to increased awareness of process convenience, digital literacy, and internet penetration across the country. Additionally, because food is an essential product for households, investors tend to invest heavily in customer loyalty. Therefore, with heavy investment in customer adoption and customer loyalty, the demand for online grocery is expected to grow further in India.

Fig 1. Kawathekar Supermarket

The central government of India has designed and developed a smart metropolis with state-of-the-art structures for building various models of e-commerce and online stores. Due to these reasons, the demand for online grocery retail is witnessing a growth rate of 25-30% in India's metros and other emerging smart metros. Online groceries currently account for just \$200 million of total demand, but reflecting trends such as product diversification and express delivery, total demand is projected to reach \$10.5 billion or \$1.2 billion by 2023. It is expected to account for \$.

Fig 2. Internal Structure of Supermarket

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Shopify - Fast and responsive solutions

Shopify is an e-commerce platform that allows small businesses to build and customize online stores. Shopify also offers his POS software for brick-and-mortar stores. Shopify integrates social networks, shopping cart and payment functionality, and order processing. Shopify is popular because it allows businesses to build an inclusive customer base. Shoppers can easily make online purchases using convenient devices such as mobile phones, tablets, and laptops.[1].

B. Amazon - Cost effective for businesses

Widely known as the world's largest digital marketplace, Amazon has changed the way we shop online. Additionally, Amazon has a separate branch focused on cloud computing and artificial intelligence. Approximately 44% of customers begin their product search on Amazon. Also, 40% buy products on the site at least once a month. For those in the e-commerce industry, Amazon can be a valuable opportunity to build profits and customer relationships. [2].

C. Flipkart Private Limited

Flipkart Private Limited is an Indian e-commerce company based in Bangalore and incorporated as a private limited company in Singapore. The company initially focused on online bookselling before expanding to order other products such as consumer electronics, fashion, household goods, groceries, and household goods. In October 2014, Flipkart repeated the Big Billion Days event as a multi-day event dedicated to his Flipkart operations. Flipkart achieved \$300 million in gross merchandise value during the event. The largest distribution value was from fashion products, and the largest value was from mobile[3].

D. Myntra

Myntra is your one-stop shop for all your fashion and lifestyle needs. Myntra, India's largest fashion and lifestyle e-commerce store, offers a wide range of brands and products on

its portal and aims to provide a hassle-free and enjoyable shopping experience to shoppers across India. Myntra generates revenue through an aggregation model. We buy seasonal products from colorful brands and sell them on our website.[4].

E. Lenskart: Eyeglasses & More

Lenskart is your #1 shopping store for eyeglasses and lacrimals, with a wide selection of eyeglasses, sunglasses, safety glasses, frames, anti-glare, contact lenses, reading glasses, computer glasses, try-on glasses at home, traditional sunglasses, and more. . and eye accessories. According to G2 Mound, Lenskart uses 53 of his technology products and services, including HTML, jQuery, and Google Analytics. According to Build With, Lenskart uses 101 technologies extensively on his website. These include "Show Port Meta," "iPhone/Mobile Compatible," and "Domain Not Resolved." [5].

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

It is very difficult for retailers to manage a large number of customers at the same time and keep records of each product. We are trying to implement a system that can provide systematic information about the products available in this online grocery delivery and management system. Provide appropriate details about products and items. Customers can browse the product catalog and add items to their shopping cart. To perform the above tasks, the customer must register and log into the system.

IV. METHODOLOGY

In recent years, there has been an increase in media coverage of e-commerce. However, the concept of e-commerce is still unfamiliar to many people due to its newness.

A. Development of methodology:

The actual methodology is developed in this phase. Detailed descriptions of each task in the methodology are documented, including the objectives, inputs, approach relevant models, applicable tools and techniques, outputs, and any references.

B. Implementation of methodology

This methodology is implemented together with the customer. This phase includes the completion of marketing and sales of e-commerce strategy development services, followed by actual implementation.

C. Revision of methodology

This phase involves finalizing and revising the methodology. Most of these revisions are based on experience with customer projects.

Fig 3. Methodology for Application

V. PROS AND CONS

A. Pros:

- Reduced overhead costs
- No need for a physical store front
- Ability to reach broader audience
- Scalability
- Trach logistics

B. Cons:

- Potential security threats
- Competition
- Shipping logistics
- iv. Limited connection with customers

VI. PROJECT SCOPE

The scope of e-commerce is vast. E-commerce has been thriving for many years and is one of the fastest growing sectors in the online world. It took some time for this to be accepted by end consumers, but we are now at a point where the majority of people enjoy shopping online. There were many concerns about online shopping when it was first introduced, but over the years, people have come to trust e-commerce for all his shopping needs.

VII. CONCLUSION

The Internet has brought so many opportunities for online business, and e-commerce is one of the most popular. In addition to requiring a small investment, it is actually a form of business that does not require a full-time commitment, especially if you sell a limited number of products. If used properly, e-commerce can prove beneficial to society, but otherwise it can lead to the destruction of the environment for future generations.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Tobias Lutke, 2006, shopify marquee shopping cart system, <https://www.shopify.com>
- [2]. Jeff Bezos, July 5,1994, Amazon cost effective for businesses, <https://www.amazon.in>
- [3]. Sachin Bansal, October 2007, Flipkart e-business services, <https://www.flipkart.com>
- [4]. Mukesh Bansal, 2007,CEO:Nandita Sinha, Myntra effective products, <https://www.myntra.com>
- [5]. Piyush Bansal, November 2010, Lenskart specs e-businesses, <https://www.lenskart.com>